

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN: 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**EVALUATION OF CHEMICAL CHANGES IN FOUR
SELECTED VARIETIES OF GRAPES UNDER THE CLIMATIC
CONDITION OF BALOCHISTAN PROVINCE****SaminaMengal*¹, Nizam Baloch¹, Tamoor Khan**², Farida Behlil³, Mohammad Faheem¹,
Murad Bibi¹, Rehana Yasmeen¹, Hafsa².**¹Department of Chemistry, University of Baluchistan, Sariab Road Quetta, Pakistan.²Faculty of Agriculture, Lesbela university of Agriculture Water and Marine Sciences, Uthal Balochistan.³Department of Chemistry, Sardar Bahadur Khan Women University, Brewery Road Quetta, Pakistan.**Abstract:**

Present study was carried out in order to evaluate the chemical changes in the grape varieties i.e. Kishmishi, Sandokhani, Sahibi and Haita, which were grown in grape areas of the Balochistan province. The results reveal that best fruit quality on the basis of biochemical analysis was observed in Kishmishi and Sandokhani varieties in Quetta district. While Sahibi and Haita variety were the best varieties in Pishin district. Averaging best quality data were observed in Mastung district, while lowest quality fruits were observed in Kalat district.

Key words: Biochemical Evaluation, Grapes varieties, Chemical changes**Corresponding author:****Tamoor Khan,**

Faculty of Agriculture,

Lesbela university of Agriculture Water and Marine Sciences,

Uthal Balochistan.

E-Mail: gumberani1@yahoo.com

QR code

Please cite this article in press as Tamoor Khan et al, *Evaluation of Chemical Changes in Four Selected Varieties of Grapes under the Climatic Condition of Balochistan Province*, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2017; 4(07).

INTRODUCTION:

Grapes (*Vitis vinifera*) belong to the family *vitaceae*. Commercially grapes are the world biggest and most widespread deciduous fruit crop [1]. Grapes are widely grown all over the world but Spain, Italy and France are major grapes growing countries [2, 3]. Grapes are Contain Sugar, Vitamins, minerals, and other important food supplements [4, 5]. Grapes are almost grown all the temperate regions of Pakistan. In Pakistan grapes are grown on an area of 3500 hectares with annual production of 35500 tones [6, 7].

Balochistan is the main pocket for grape production. The area under grape in Balochistan is about 3400 hectares with the production of about 34300 tones. Most growing areas of grape in Balochistan are Quetta, Kalat, Mastung, Pishin, Zairat, Loralai, Kanak, Khuzdar etc.[8]. Production of grape is increasing day-by-day and replacing apple due to high resistant against drought conditions [3]. Quality of Fruit grapes is different in all areas due to little bit soil and climatically conditions, this may lead new physiogenic races which results variation in quality of fruit. Keeping in view the importance of grapes and change in morphology changes it was decided to carry out a planned work for evaluation bio-chemical changes in grapes varieties grown in different areas.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:**Collection of plant material**

Four varieties of grapes (Kishmishi, Sandokhani, Sahibi and Haita) were collected from Quetta, Kalat, Mastung and Pishin field areas.

**Evaluation of Chemical changes in grape varieties
Elemental analysis**

Five (5) grams dried berry from each variety of all areas were digested in 20-30 ml HNO₃ (Nitric Acid) through gently heating for digestion. After completed digestion each sample was filtered and volume was made to 100 ml by adding distilled water in volumetric Flask. The elemental analysis was done through Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer with of standard and blank solution Sodium was determined by Flam Photometer wherever required [9-11].

Analysis of dry matter and moisture

100 gm sample was taken from each variety for dry matter and moisture analysis. These samples were kept in Electric oven for two hours at 54 C°. The dry matter and Moisture were analyzed as [12].

Moisture = Total wt. of sample before oven dry-wt. of sample.

Dry matter = Total weight after over dry [13, 14].

Analysis of fat

The fat% age was estimated by extracting fat from grapes samples in Soxtech system through solvent Diethyl ether as; took 10 grams for every sample in crucible putting it into thimble containing diethyl ether and connected this thimble to the adaptor in a manner that knobs of extraction unit were in the rising position and general knobs were in the boiling position. The temperature was adjusted according to solvent boiling point. The process was done about 2 hours. Finely the solvent diethyl ether was evaporated. The extracted fat percentage was calculated by using formula as.

$$\% \text{ of Extract} = \frac{\text{Wt. of extracted} \times 100}{\text{Wt. of sample}}$$

[15, 16].

Analysis of sugar

Analysis of Sugar was done through U.V. Spectrophotometer by taking 10 gm. Berry from every sample and added in hot redistilled alcohol to which enough precipitated Calcium Carbonate has also been added for neutralizing acidity. These were allowed for water contents of test portion. Heated up boiling point on steam in water both for about 30 minutes [17,18].

Finally discounted solution into volumetric flask and allowed to cool. Prepared samples were subjected for sugar analysis and through UV Spectrophotometer [19].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:**Evaluation of chemical changes in grape varieties**

Table 1: Variation of bioactive compounds due to cultivated area in grapes variety “Kishmishi”

BIOACTIVE COMPOUNDS	QUETTA	KALAT	KANAK	MASTUNG	PISHIN
Moisture	78%	76%	80%	79%	82%
Dry matter	20%	21%	19%	18%	19%
Sugar	23%	18%	24%	24%	16%
Fat	1.2%	1.0%	1.6%	1.0%	0.9%
Phosphorus	0.0012%	0.0011%	0.0013%	0.0013%	0.0010%
Potassium	0.0020%	0.0019%	0.0020%	0.0020%	0.0012%
Sodium	0.0040%	0.0033%	0.0037%	0.0036%	0.0020%
Iron	0.0080%	0.0078%	0.0087%	0.0082%	0.0058%
Zinc	0.0012%	0.0011%	0.0012%	0.0012%	0.004%

The data in table-1 regarding bioactive compounds shows that the moisture remained to increase at 82-80-79% in Pishin, Kanak and Mastung field areas. However, with the term of sugar, remained perpetual at 23-24% and were observed at Kanak, Mastung and Quetta field areas respectively. Hence, relevant results further, showed that best fruit quality on the basis of biochemical analysis was observed in Kishmishi varieties which were grown in Quetta field areas.

Table 2: Variation of Bioactive compounds due to cultivated area in grapes variety “Sahibi”

BIOACTIVE COMPOUNDS	QUETTA	KALAT	KANAK	MASTUNG	PASHIN
Moisture	70%	71%	78%	79%	80%
Dry matter	22%	23%	20%	20%	18%
Sugar	18%	17%	20%	19%	22%
Fat	0.9%	0.7%	1.0%	1.1%	2.9%
Phosphorus	0.0098%	0.0010%	0.0012%	0.0012%	0.0014%
Potassium	0.0019%	0.0018%	0.0019%	0.0019%	0.0024%
Sodium	0.0033%	0.0033%	0.0035%	0.0034%	0.0060%
Iron	0.0040%	0.0039%	0.0066%	0.0066%	0.0108%
Zinc	0.0073%	0.0060%	0.0010%	0.0010%	0.0014%

The information in table-2 about bioactive compounds displays that the moisture remained to increase at 80-79-78% in Pishin, Mastung and Kanak field areas. While, with the term of dry matter, persisted at 23-22% and were observed at Kalat and Quetta field areas respectively. Henceforth, pertinent outcomes are presented that the Sahibi variety was best fruit quality in Pishin field areas.

Table 3: Variation of Bioactive compounds due to cultivated area in grapes Variety “Sandokhani”

BIOACTIVE COMPOUNDS	QUETTA	KALAT	KANAK	MASTUNG	PASHIN
Moisture	76%	76%	79%	81%	82%
Dry matter	18%	17%	19%	18%	16%
Sugar	29%	24%	28%	28%	18%
Fat	2.2%	1.8%	2.0%	2.01%	0.6%
Phosphorus	0.0020%	0.0017%	0.0018%	0.0018%	0.0012%
Potassium	0.0031%	0.0030%	0.0030%	0.0031%	0.0017%
Sodium	0.0056%	0.0050%	0.0046%	0.0045%	0.0022%
Iron	0.0089%	0.0090%	0.0878%	0.0087%	0.0064%
Zinc	0.0022%	0.0018%	0.0017%	0.0017%	0.0014%

Present research was evaluated in order to determine the chemical changes in grape varieties as shown in table-3. The data further, depicted about bioactive compounds displays that the dry matter endured at 82-81-79% in Pishin, Mastung and Kanak field areas respectively. While, with the term of dry matter, keep on at 19-18% and were perceived at Kanak, Mastung and Quetta field areas separately. Henceforward, relevant results, showed that the Sandokhani was the best quality of fruits in Quetta field areas.

Table 4: Variation of Bioactive compounds due to cultivated area in grapes variety "Haita"

BIOACTIVE COMPOUNDS	QUETTA	KALAT	KANAK	MASTUNG	PASHIN
Moisture	77%	73%	75%	75%	76%
Dry matter	21%	23%	18%	19%	18%
Sugar	16%	19%	23%	23%	26%
Fat	1.0%	0.9%	2.00%	2.0%	2.9%
Phosphorus	0.0018%	0.0017%	0.0019%	0.0019%	0.0031%
Potassium	0.0019%	0.0018%	0.0029%	0.0029%	0.0030%
Sodium	0.0047%	0.0043%	0.0052%	0.0052%	0.0060%
Iron	0.0071%	0.0049%	0.0098%	0.0097%	0.0098%
Zinc	0.0013%	0.0012%	0.0018%	0.0018%	0.0034%

Table-3 shows about bioactive compounds displays that the dry matter recorded at 77-76-75% in Quetta, Pishin, Mastung and Kanak field areas separately. Therefore, significant outcomes, were exhibited that fruit quality in Haita was best grown at Pishin field areas.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS:

Averaging best quality fruit in all four varieties were observed in the areas of Kanak and Mastung while, lowest quality fruits in all grapes varieties were observed in Kalat area. Pertinent outcomes, presented that the Sahibi variety was best fruit quality in Pishin field areas. Relevant results further, showed that the Sandokhani best quality was grown in Quetta field areas. Results showed that the Sandokhani was considered as the best quality fruits in Quetta field areas. Based on results fowling recommendation was formulated. Notwithstanding, the potential pocket of the grape fruits at Balochistan province, the grower did not deemed to grown the low delta fruit like grape, in this regard it should be suggested that the promotion and propagation should be at large scale or vast areas in order to increase the farmers socio-economic condition.

REFERENCES:

- Lohan O P, Lall D, Vaid J and Negi S. Grapes and it chemical variation. Indian Journal of Animal Science. 2002 53:1057-106
- Barry T N and Duncan S J. The role of condensed tannins in the nutritional value of Lotus pedunculatus for sheep I. Voluntary intake.. Journal of Association of Official Analytical Chemists 1984. 65:496-497
- Holecheck J L, 1984 Comparative contribution of grapes, for nutrition and bio-chemicals. J Food Sci. 1984:261-263.
- Ammar H, López S, González JS, Ranilla MJ. Chemical composition and in vitro digestibility of

some Spanish browse plant species. Journal of the Science of Food and Agriculture. 2004 Jan 30;84(2):197-204.

5. Kumar R and Sing M, Grapes and its nutritional value. Journal of Agriculture and Food Chemistry. 1984 32: 447-453

6. Ghafoor K, Choi YH, Jeon JY, Jo IH. Optimization of ultrasound-assisted extraction of phenolic compounds, antioxidants, and anthocyanins from grape (*Vitis vinifera*) seeds. Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry. 2009 Apr 30;57(11):4988-94.

7. Khair SM, Ahmad M, Khan E. Profitability analysis of grapes orchards in Pishin: an ex-post analysis. Sarhad Journal of Agriculture. 2009;25(1):103-11.

7. Anonymous, 2000 Agriculture Statistics Balochistan Agric Dept. Balochistan pp: 27.

8. Balogun RO, Jones RJ, Holmes JG. Digestibility of some tropical browse species varying in tannin content. Animal Feed Science and Technology. 1998 Dec 1;76(1):77-88.

9. Frutos P, Hervás G, Ramos G, Giráldez FJ, Mantecon AR. Condensed tannin content of several shrub species from a mountain area in northern Spain, and its relationship to various indicators of nutritive value. Animal Feed Science and Technology. 2002 Feb 25;95(3):215-26.

10. Sérgio S, Rivero-Pérez MD, Correia AC, Jordão AM, González-San José ML. Analysis of commercial grape raisins: phenolic content,

antioxidant capacity and radical scavenger activity. *Ciência e Técnica Vitivinícola*. 2014 Jan 1;29(1).

11.Cheng G, Fa JQ, Xi ZM, Zhang ZW. Research on the quality of the wine grapes in corridor area of China. *Food Science and Technology (Campinas)*. 2015 Mar;35(1):38-44.

12.AOAC, Official Method of Analysis (Association of Official Analytical Chemists) Washington, DC. USA. 2014 .20th edition Pp.66-88

13.Parker TL, Wang XH, Pazmiño J, Engeseth NJ. Antioxidant capacity and phenolic content of grapes, sun-dried raisins, and golden raisins and their effect on ex vivo serum antioxidant capacity. *Journal of agricultural and food chemistry*. 2007 Sep 20;55(21):8472-7.

14.Albrecht KA, Broderick GA. Degradation of forage legume protein by rumen microorganisms. *Agronomy Abstract*. American Society of Agronomy, Madison, WI. 1990:185.

15.Abdrabba S, Hussein S. Chemical composition of pulp, seed and peel of red grape from Libya. *Global Journal of Scientific Researches Journal*. 2015;3(2):6-11.

16.Alvira P, Rebole A, Gonzalez G. Chemical-bromatological valorisation of the grapevines. *Avances en Alimentacion y Mejora Animal*. 1983;26:472-8.

17.Sensoy RI. Determination of organic acids, sugars, and macro-micro nutrient contents of must in some grape (*Vitis vinifera* L.) cultivars. *JAPS: Journal of Animal & Plant Sciences*. 2015 Jun 1;25(3).

18.Varandas S, Teixeira MJ, Marques JC, Aguiar A, Alves A, Bastos MM. Glucose and fructose levels on grape skin: interference in *Lobesia botrana* behaviour. *Analytica chimica acta*. 2004 Jun 18;513(1):351-5.